

The Use of Linear Least Squares Regression Method (LLSRM) for Estimating Petroleum Reserves in Niger Delta Region of Nigeria

Oseh, J. O.¹; Oguamah, I. A.²; and Ogunkunle, F.T.³

1, 2Department of Chemical and Petroleum Engineering, Afe Babalola University, Ado – Ekiti (ABUAD), Nigeria.

3Department of Chemical and Petroleum Engineering, Madonna University, Enugu Campus, Enugu State, Nigeria

*Corresponding author: Oseh, J. O. E-mail: jeffreydengr@gmail.com,

Received: November 14, 2014, Accepted: December 29, 2014, Published: December 29, 2014.

ABSTRACT

Hydrocarbon reserves are basic to planning and investment decisions in Petroleum Industry. Therefore its proper estimation is of considerable importance in oil and gas production. The estimation of hydrocarbon reserves in the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria has been very popular, and very successful, in the Nigerian oil and gas industry for the past 50 years. In order to fully estimate the hydrocarbon potentials in Nigerian Niger Delta Region, a clear understanding of the reserve geology and production history should be acknowledged. Reserves estimation of most fields is often performed through Material Balance and Volumetric methods. Alternatively a simple Estimation Model and Least Squares Regression may be useful or appropriate. This model is based on extrapolation of additional reserve due to exploratory drilling trend and the additional reserve factor which is due to revision of the existing fields. The Estimation Model and the Linear Regression Analysis used in this study gives improved estimates of the fields considered, hence can be used in other Nigerian Fields with recent production history.

Keywords: Petroleum Reserves, Estimation Model, Linear Least Squares Regression Method, Niger Delta, Estimated Reserves, Actual Reserves.

INTRODUCTION

The process of estimating oil and gas reserves for a producing field continues throughout the life of the field. There is always uncertainty in making such estimates. The level of uncertainty is affected by the following factors: Reservoir type, Source of reservoir energy, Quantity and quality of the geological, engineering, and geophysical data, Assumptions adopted when making the estimate, Available technology, and Experience and knowledge of the evaluator [1]. The magnitude of uncertainty, however, decreases with time until the economic limit is reached and the ultimate recovery is realized [1]. Petroleum (or any other natural resource) reserves cannot be measured directly. They are estimates of future production under certain conditions which may or may not be well specified, but which include economic assumptions, knowledge of the feasibility of projects to extract the resources, and geological information. Judgment is involved and different estimates for the same field are legitimately possible [2].

Statistical estimation of oil and gas reserves is the estimation of petroleum reserves using historical records of production, exploratory drilling, pressure history and other factors that influence reserves [3]. Reserve estimation is useful in evaluation of exploration and development expenditures, to determine the market value of a field in connection with possible purchase or sale. It is also used to determine the feasibility of secondary recovery projects and other special recovery projects. Reserves can be divided into primary and secondary reserves. Primary reserves is the estimated future commercial production recoverable by normal or primary method as a result of energy

availability in the reservoir while secondary reserve is the estimated future commercial production which will be recovered in addition to the primary reserves as a result of pressure maintenance, water flooding or other secondary methods [4]. Unproved reserves are less certain to be recovered than proved reserves and may be sub-classified as probable or possible to denote increasing uncertainty. Proved reserves can be estimated with reasonable certainty to be recoverable under current economic conditions which include prices and costs prevailing at the time of the estimate [5]. Proved reserves may be developed or under developed. It must have facilities to process and transport those reserves to markets that are operational at the time of the estimate or there is commitment or reasonable expectation to install such facilities in the future [5]. The additional reserve each year is dependent on reserves found by exploratory drilling in new pools, in new fields and reserves done to re-evaluate the basic geological and engineering data of existing fields. A discovery during one year will result in the drilling of additional wells during subsequent production and these wells add productive acreage to the previously estimated proved area [6]. Other reserves estimation methods includes: Analogy, Volumetric, Decline analysis, Material balance, and Reservoir simulation [7]. Most of the field data required are not obtainable until the reservoir has produced for substantial period, therefore evaluated reserve of new field using other reserves estimation methods are not reliable.

Aims of the Study

The aims of this study are to estimate the petroleum reserves in

the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria and to select the best statistical method for estimating hydrocarbon reserves. A mathematical model for petroleum reserves estimate based on extrapolation of exploratory drilling trend was developed. Additional reserve factor due to revision of existing field is included in the model. Linear Least Squares Regression Method (LLSRM) is employed to solve the constants in the developed model.

Geological Settings of the Niger Delta Region Of Nigeria

Niger Delta is a large arcuate Tertiary prograding sedimentary complex deposited under transitional marine, deltaic, and continental environments since Eocene in the North to Pliocene in the South. Located within the Cenozoic formation of Southern Nigeria in West Africa, it covers an area of about 75,000 Km [8] from the Calabar Flank and Abakaliki Trough in Eastern Nigeria to the Benin Flank in the West, and it opens to the Atlantic ocean in the South where it protrudes into the Gulf of Guinea as an extension from the Benue Trough and Anambra Basin provinces [9]. The Niger Delta as a prograding sedimentary complex is characterized by a coarsening upward regressive sequences. The overall regressive sequence of clastic sediments was deposited in a series of offlap cycles that were interrupted by periods of sea level change [10]. These periods resulted in episodes of erosion or marine transgression. Stratigraphically, the Tertiary Niger Delta is divided into three Formations, namely Akata Formation, Agbada Formation, and Benin Formation [11]. The Akata Formation at the base of the delta is predominantly undercompacted, overpressured sequence of thick marine shales, clays and siltstones (potential source rock) with turbidite sandstones (potential reservoirs in deep water). It is estimated that the formation is up to 7,000 meters thick [12]. The Agbada Formation, the major petroleum-bearing unit about 3700m thick, is alternation sequence of paralic sandstones, clays and siltstone and it is reported to show a two-fold division [13]. The upper Benin Formation overlying Agbada Formation consists of massive, unconsolidated continental sandstones.

Why “linear least squares regression method (llsrm)” for petroleum reserves?

The “Method of Least Squares” that is used to estimate parameters estimates was independently developed in the late 1700’s and the early 1800’s by the mathematician Karl Friedrich Gauss, Adrien Marie Legendre and Robert Adrain [14], [15], [16] working in Germany, France and America respectively. In the least squares method the unknown parameters are estimated by minimizing the sum of the squared derivatives between the data and the model. The minimization process reduces the over-determined system of equations formed by the data to a sensible system of p (where p is the number of parameters in the functional part of the model) equations in p unknowns. This new system of equations is then solved to obtain the parameter estimates [16]. Linear Least Squares Regression Method (LLSRM) is by far the most widely used modeling method adapted to a broad range of situations that are outside its direct scope. It plays a strong underlying role in many other modeling methods like Non Linear Least Squares Regression Method, Weighted Least Squares Regression, and LOESS [14]. Linear Least Squares Regression Method (LLSRM) can be used directly with an appropriate data set to fit complex data. It has earned its place as the primary tool for process modeling because of its effectiveness

and completeness. Though there are types of data that are better described by functions that are non-linear in the parameters, many process in science and engineering are well described by linear models. This is because either the processes are inherently linear or because, over short range, any process can be well-approximated by a linear model. The estimates of the unknown parameters obtained from linear least squares regression are the optimal estimates from a broad class of possible parameter estimates under the usual assumptions used for process modeling. Practically speaking, Linear Least Squares Regression Method (LLSRM) makes very efficient use of the data. Good results can be obtained with relatively small data sets [17].

ESTIMATION MODEL DEVELOPMENT

Theory of the model

The model is based on the principle that the reserve at the end of any year will be the sum of the reserve at the beginning of that year and additional reserve minus productions during that year. Additional reserves of hydrocarbons in any year are broken down into two established categories: Those attributable to recoveries are as a result of exploratory effort in new pools in new fields. Reserves attributed to revisions are as a result of re-evaluation on the existing fields. Newly discovered petroleum reservoirs, even in existing fields are always fully developed during the year of recovery [18]. Therefore, the year and reserve estimates of discoveries generally represent only a part of the reserves that will ultimately be assigned to these new reservoirs. A discovery during one year will usually result in the drilling of additional wells during subsequent years and generally these new wells will increase the previously estimated productive area [19]. Additional producing wells in a reservoir not only add to the estimated productive area but also help to improve the basic geologic and engineering data. Early estimates of porosity, interstitial water, pay thickness and other important reservoir factors may be reviewed therefore from future wells. As field development continues, production history accumulates and the most accurate methods of pressure maintenance and secondary recovery factor are formulated [20].

Estimation Model Derivation

Reserve at the end of any year is defined as:

$$R_x = R(x-1) + R_x^+ - Q_x + A_x \quad (1.1)$$

Where,

X is the number of terms in years.

R_x is the estimated reserve at the end of x th year.

$R(x-1)$ is the estimated reserve at the end of $(x-1)$ th year.

R_x^+ is the additional reserve during the x th year due to exploratory drilling.

Q_x is the production in the x th year

A_x is the additional reserve in the x th year due to revision of existing fields.

Additional reserve due to exploratory drilling R_x^+ based on historical trend is defined as:

$$R_x^+ = (m + nP_x) - C_{x-1} \quad (1.2)$$

Where,

m is the intercept of regression line of plot of cumulative additional reserve against cumulative number of completed wells.

n is the rate of change of cumulative additional reserve with cumulative number of completed wells.

P_x is the cumulative number of completed wells at the end of

xth year.

C_{x-1} is the cumulative additional reserve at the end of (x-1)th year.

In general, $(m + nP_x)$ represents cumulative additional reserve due to exploratory effort in the xth year. Thus, it can be represented by C_x .

$$C_x = m + nP_x \quad (1.3)$$

Where,

C_x is the cumulative additional reserve in the xth year. The Estimation Model can therefore be approximated as:

$$R_x = R(x-1) + C_x - C_{x-1} - Q_x + A_x \quad (1.4)$$

$$R_x = R(x-1) + (m + nP_x) - C_{x-1} - Q_x + A_x \quad (1.5)$$

$$R_x = R(x-1) + (m + nP_x) + A_x - (C_{x-1} + Q_x) \quad (1.6)$$

Constants m and n can be calculated by Linear Least Squares Regression Method (LLSRM).

Equation (1.6) represents the general form of the Estimation Model.

Linear Least Squares Regression Method (LLSRM)

The concept of linear regression is concerned with an investigation of the dependence of one variable on a linear combination of independent variable. When the dependent variable is expressed linearly in terms of one independent variable, the linear expression is said to be simple while it is said to be multiple when the dependent variables is expressed linearly in terms of several independent variables. In this study, the linear regression is simple since only one independent variable is involved.

From Equation (1.3),

$$C_x = m + nP_x$$

C_x from this equation is the calculated C_x which may not correspond to the observed C_x .

Let C_x' = observed C_x .

Then the error term, T_x is calculated as:

$$T_x = C_x - C_x' \quad (1.7)$$

$$T_x = (nP_x + m) \quad (1.8)$$

To minimize the error, a relation of the form is introduced:

$$S = \sum T_x^2 \quad (1.9)$$

Using least squares to minimize S, so that

$$\frac{ds}{dT} = 0; \frac{ds}{dm} = 0$$

$$\frac{ds}{dn} = 2 \sum T_x \frac{dT_x}{dn} = 0$$

$$= 2 \sum (nP_x + m - C_x) P_x = 0$$

$$= n \sum P_x^2 + m \sum P_x - \sum C_x P_x = 0$$

Therefore,

$$\sum C_x P_x = m \sum P_x + n \sum P_x^2 \quad (2.0)$$

Similarly,

$$\frac{ds}{dm} = 2 \sum T_x \frac{dT_x}{dm} = 0$$

$$= 2 \sum (nP_x + m - C_x) \times 1 = 0$$

$$= n \sum P_x + m - \sum C_x = 0$$

$$= n \sum P_x + km - \sum C_x = 0$$

Therefore,

$$\sum C_x = km + n \sum P_x \quad (2.1)$$

Where,

k is the number of data used in trend analysis. Equations (2.0) and (2.1) can then be solved simultaneously to obtain m and n.

$$\sum C_x = km + n \sum P_x$$

$$\sum C_x P_x = m \sum P_x + n \sum P_x^2$$

Or

$$\sum P_x C_x = m k \sum P_x + n (\sum P_x)^2 \quad (2.2)$$

$$k \sum C_x P_x = m k \sum P_x + n \sum P_x^2 \quad (2.3)$$

$$k \sum C_x - (\sum P_x) (\sum C_x) = (k \sum P_x^2 - (\sum P_x)^2)$$

$$n = \frac{k \sum C_x P_x - \sum P_x C_x}{(k \sum P_x^2 - (\sum P_x)^2)} \quad (2.4)$$

Substitute equation (2.4) in equation in equation (2.1)

$$\sum C_x = km + \frac{k \sum P_x \sum C_x P_x - (\sum P_x)^2 \sum C_x}{(k \sum P_x^2 - (\sum P_x)^2)}$$

$$m = \frac{\sum C_x}{k} - \frac{1}{k} \frac{k \sum P_x \sum C_x P_x - (\sum P_x)^2 \sum C_x}{(k \sum P_x^2 - (\sum P_x)^2)} \quad (2.5)$$

$C_x = m + nP_x$ represents equation of regression line on C_x and P_x .

Concept of Correlation and Standard error of estimate

Correlation is the degree of relationship between variables, in this case, the cumulated additional reserves and cumulated number of completed wells. The coefficient of correlation can be determined using the Pearson's Product-Moment Method.

$$r = k \frac{k \sum P_x C_x - (\sum P_x) \sum C_x}{\sqrt{(k \sum P_x^2 - (\sum P_x)^2) (k \sum C_x^2 - (\sum C_x)^2)}} \quad (2.6)$$

Standard error of estimate S is a measure of the scatter about the regression line and is supplied by the quantity.

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum C_x^2 - m(\sum C_x) - n \sum C_x P_x}{k}} \quad (2.7)$$

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The general form of the estimation model is given by:

$$R_x = R(x-1) + C_x - C_{x-1} - Q_x + A_x$$

Where,

R_x = Estimated reserve at the end of xth year.

$R(x-1)$ = Estimated reserve at the end of (x-1)th year.

C_x = Cumulative additional reserve during the xth year due to exploratory drilling at the end of xth year.

C_{x-1} = Cumulative additional reserve at the end of (x-1)th year.

Q_x = Production during the year.

A_x = Additional reserve in the xth year due to revision of existing fields.

$$C_x = (m + nP_x)$$

Where,

P_x is the intercept of regression line of plot of cumulative additional reserve against cumulative number of completed wells.

m and n are constant determined from linear regression model.

Estimation of Fields X and Y Reserves in Niger Delta

Two fields considered in Niger Delta region of Nigeria were assigned X and Y fields due to the sensitive nature of the data [21].

The estimation model is:

$$R_x = R(x-1) + (m + nP_x) + A_x - (C_{x-1} + Q_x).$$

A_x was assumed to be zero, i.e. no revision of the existing fields used in the reserve estimation.

The above equation reduces to:

$$R_x = R(x-1) + (m + nP_x) + A_x - (C_{x-1} + Q_x). \quad (2.8)$$

Coefficient of Correlation

The correlation between the cumulative additional reserve and cumulative number of completed wells can be estimated from equation 2.6 using the data shown in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 1: Estimated Coefficient of Correlation for Field X and Y

Field	Coefficient of Correlation, r
X	0.999817
Y	0.993728

The result from Table 1 shows that there is a perfect correlation between cumulative additional reserve and cumulative number of completed wells in the positive direction for both fields.

Table 2: Production History of Field X (2014)

Year	Annual Production (mmmbbls)	Reserves (mmmbbls)	Additional Reserve (mmmbbls)	Cumulative Additional Reserve (mmmbbls)	Cumulative No. of Completed Wells
1978	0.0301	0.615	0.0348	0.3048	18
1979	0.0304	0.594	0.0098	0.0446	24
1980	0.0363	0.560	0.0022	0.0468	25
1981	0.0217	0.597	0.0587	0.1055	55
1982	0.0318	0.571	0.0053	0.1108	58
1983	0.0258	0.554	0.0090	0.1198	62
1984	0.0286	0.529	0.0041	0.1239	64

Table 3: Production History of Field Y (2014)

Year	Annual Production (mmmbbls)	Reserve (mmmbbls)	Additional reserves (mmmbbls)	Cumulative additional reserve (mmmbbls)	Cumulative No. of completed wells
1978	0.0150	0.116	0.0201	0.0201	1.0
1979	0.0153	0.142	0.0413	0.0614	31
1980	0.0133	0.144	0.0148	0.0762	38
1981	0.0088	0.138	0.0026	0.0788	41
1982	0.0057	0.133	0.0009	0.0797	42
1983	0.0064	0.128	0.0012	0.0809	44
1984	0.0054	0.123	0.0008	0.0817	45

Determination of constants n and m from Table 2 and 3 from equation (2.4) and (2.5) respectively

Field	n	m
X	0.1949×10^7	$- 0.1440 \times 10^7$
Y	0.1807×10^7	0.3607×10^7

Applying the constants generated from equation (2.4) and (2.5) respectively to the developed estimation model of equation (1.6) for Field X and Y gives the results in Tables 4 and 5 respectively.

Table 4: Annual Estimated Reserves and Actual Reserves for Field X (2014)

Year	Estimated Reserves (mmmbbls)	Actual Reserves (mmmbbls)	Difference
1979	0.596092	0.59420	0.001892
1980	0.561740	0.56010	0.001640
1981	0.598499	0.59710	0.001399
1982	0.527544	0.57060	0.000739
1983	0.554539	0.55380	0.000739
1984	0.529836	0.52930	0.000536

Table 5: Annual Estimated Reserve and Actual Reserve for Field Y (2014)

Year	Estimated Reserves (mmmbbls)	Actual Reserves (mmmbbls)	Difference
1979	0.138946	0.142300	0.003354
1980	0.138295	0.143300	0.005505
1981	0.134915	0.137600	0.002684
1982	0.131022	0.132800	0.001778
1983	0.128236	0.127600	0.000636
1984	0.124643	0.123000	0.001643

Fig. 1: Cumulative Additional Reserves vs. Cumulative No. of Completed Wells for Field X

Fig. 2: Cumulative Additional Reserve vs. Cumulative No. of Completed Wells for Field Y

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

It is observed that the rate of change of cumulative additional reserves with cumulative number of completed wells varies from one field to the other and it is a function of hydrocarbon potential of each field. A field with high hydrocarbon potential has a high rate of change of cumulative number of completed wells. For example the rate of change of cumulative additional reserves with cumulative number of completed wells of Field Y is larger than that of Field X. It shows that Field Y has a huge crude oil potential than Field X. Therefore the developed Estimation Model could be used as a benchmark to measure the hydrocarbon potential of a given field.

The variation between the estimated reserve and the actual reserve could be attributed to the assumption made in the application of the estimation model that no revision of the field samples has been used which makes the additional reserve due to the revision of the field to be zero. The additional reserve when added by way of revision could alter the reserve potential when increased knowledge of the field changes the field fractional recovery.

CONCLUSIONS

The following conclusions could be drawn from the findings:

- ❖ The Estimation model is useful in that better and more reliable reserve estimates are evaluated since the most recent data are used.
- ❖ The model gives an improved performance when compared between cumulative additional reserve and cumulative number of completed wells.
- ❖ The model depends on sound, accurate and up to date

production data. Direct estimation of reserves in future will not be possible without first estimating the production during the year and reserve at the end of the preceding year.

- ❖ Reserves estimates of some existing fields could be considerably improved upon if such fields are revised by way of re-evaluating their basic geology and engineering data.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- ❖ The model only investigated the reserves in existing wells. Effort should be geared towards evaluating reserves of unexpected fields.
- ❖ A mathematical expression that would relate the rate of change of cumulative additional reserve to cumulative number of completed wells be developed and incorporated into the model to replace the one evaluated from linear regression analysis.

REFERENCES

1. Arps, J.J., Estimation of primary oil reserves: Transactions AIME (Journal of Petroleum Technology), vol. 207, (1956), pp. 182-191.
2. Ross, J.G. Petroleum Resources Classification and Definitions. The Guidelines for the Evaluation of Petroleum Reserves and Resources, (2001), pp. 6-11. 25 Richardson, Texas: SPE.
3. "Standards Pertaining to the Estimating and Auditing of Oil and Gas Reserve Information," SPE, Richardson, Texas (December 1979).
4. Cronquist, C. Estimation and Classification of Reserves of Crude Oil, Natural Gas, and Condensate. Richardson, Texas: SPE, (2001).
5. Guidelines for the Evaluation of Petroleum Reserves and Resources. A Supplement to the SPE/WPC Petroleum Reserves Definitions and the SPE/WPC/AAPG Petroleum Resources Definitions (2001), pp. 1-7, 131-137.
6. Jacks, H.H. Forecasting Future Performance. Reservoir Simulation, C.C. Mattox and R.L. Dalton eds., Vol. 13, (1990), pp. 99-110. Richardson, Texas: Monograph Series, SPE.
7. Dake, L. P. The Practice of Reservoir Engineering. Amsterdam: Elsevier Scientific Publishing Co. pp. 23-44, (1978).
8. Arps, J. J., & Ertekin, T. "Statistical Analysis of Crude Oil Recovery and Recovery Efficiency," Bulletin D14, (1967), American Petroleum Institute, Washington D.C.
9. Burke, R. C., Desauvagie, T. F. J., & Whiteman, A. J. Geological History of the Benue Valley and adjacent areas. (1972), University press: Ibadan.
10. Etu-Efeotor, J. O. Fundamentals of Petroleum Geology. Paragraphics: (1997), pp. 21-23, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria.
11. Ekweozor, C. M., & Daukoro, E. M. Petroleum source bed evaluation of Tertiary Niger Delta-reply: American Association of Petroleum Geologists Bulletin, vol. 68, (1984). pp. 390-394.
12. Bouvier, J. D., Kaars-Sijpesteijn, C. H., Kluener, D. F., & Onyejekwe, C. C. "Three-dimensional Seismic Interpretation and Fault sealing Investigations". Nun River Field, Nigeria. AAPG Bulletin 73(11): (1989), 1397-1414.
13. Doust, H., & Omatsola, E. Niger Delta. "Divergent/passive Margin Basins". AAPG Memoir 48: (1990), 239-248.
14. Stigler, S. M. "Mathematical Statistics in the early state". The

- Annals of Statistics, vol. 6, (1978), pp. 239-265
15. Harter, H. L. The method of Least Squares and some alternatives. *International Statistical Review* 42: (1976), 147-174, 235-264, 282.
 16. Stigler, S. M. *The History of Statistics. The measurement of Uncertainty Before 1900*, The Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts, pp. 56-87, (1986).
 17. Larry, J. S. "Theory and Problems of Beginning Statistics" (Schaum's Outline Series), McGraw Hill, pp. 309-330, (1998).
 18. John, M. "Petroleum Reserves in Question" Sustainable Development Programme SDP BP 04/03 (October 2004), pp. 23-56.
 19. Mistrot, Gus A. *Reserves Estimating-Common Errors and How to Avoid Them*. (1998), pp. 39-44, Richardson, Texas: SPE Short Course, SPE.
 20. McMichael, C. and Spencer, A. "Operational Issues" *The Guidelines for the Evaluation of Petroleum Reserves and Resources*, (2001), pp. 5-10, 21-26. Society of Petroleum Engineers, 222 Palisades Creek Drive Richardson, TX 75080-2040, USA.
 21. Department of Petroleum Resources (2014), No. 7, Kofo Abayomi Street, Victoria Island, Lagos State, Nigeria.

Citation: Oseh, J. O. et al., (2014) The Use of Linear Least Squares Regression Method (LLSRM) for Estimating Petroleum Reserves in Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. *J. of Advancement in Engineering and Technology*. V2I2. DOI: 10.15297/JAET.V2I2.03

Copyright: © 2014 Oseh, J. O.. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.